

Integrating Artificial Intelligence in Higher Education: A Case Study of Cambodian Universities

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Abstract:

Artificial intelligence (AI) is rapidly transforming education, offering exciting opportunities and challenges for universities. This study investigates the integration of AI in undergraduate studies at three universities in Battambang, Cambodia. The author employed a quantitative survey design targeting 370 students across various majors and year levels. This research aims to (1) examine the correlation between students' utilization of AI tools and their chosen field of study; (2) explore undergraduate students' perceptions regarding the application of AI in their academic research; and (3) analyze the perceived significance of AI integration within the

context of specific majors. Through a quantitative research approach, data were collected from 370 students across three universities, and their use, perceptions, and significance of AI in their academic endeavors were examined. The findings reveal high engagement with AI tools, particularly for language translation and writing enhancement, although most students lack formal training in AI usage. While students appreciate the efficiency and personalized learning experiences offered by AI, they also express concerns about data privacy, algorithmic biases, and the impact on critical thinking skills.

Keywords: *Integration, Artificial Intelligence, Undergraduate, Battambang.*

Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) has emerged as a force for transformation in industries, economies and societies. Within the realm of education, AI presents both prospects and hurdles with the incorporation of innovative AI tools. The growing prevalence of AI over time has brought about changes across different sectors, including education. Universities are progressively acknowledging the advantages that AI can offer in enhancing their position (George & Wooden, 2023; Tieng et al., 2023). One of the benefits of incorporating AI into education is the enhancement of student engagement, motivation and achievement. By utilizing AI-powered tools, students can receive feedback to

identify and address their weaknesses effectively, leading to learning results. According to reports, Sol et al. (2024) seem to be the first to investigate how university students majoring in English see the application of AI-powered tools in higher education. The study revealed that most Cambodian students (approximately 90%) had used AI-powered tools such as Grammarly, QuillBot, Google Translate, and ChatGPT; however, the majority of them (approximately 70%) had not received any prior training on the use of AI. The data were drawn from 328 university students' responses to an online questionnaire. Additionally, the survey revealed that university students majoring in Cambodian English tended to use AI to help them learn English through language translation services

such as Google Translate, finish research projects and assignments, and enhance their overall learning outcomes. Moreover, the integration of generative AI has the potential to completely transform education by giving teachers and students access to a wealth of resources and tools that will enable them to create, collaborate, and participate in ways that were previously unattainable. With the help of AI-driven educational technology, students will be equipped with the skills they need to succeed in the twenty-first century and beyond. These tools include individualized learning experiences and adaptive feedback systems (Jameel & Arsalan, 2024). Although AI offers benefits, students have expressed concerns, such as the accuracy and reliability of AI, which results in a lack of human interaction and potentially negative impacts on critical thinking skills from excessive reliance on AI and the ethical risks associated with its improper use (Sarin & Kimkong, 2024). Moreover, integrating AI into settings poses challenges such as data privacy issues, algorithmic biases and ensuring the ethical use of AI tools. It is crucial for educators, policymakers and tech experts to prioritize safeguarding student privacy and promoting transparency in algorithm-driven decision-making processes. The effective implementation of AI in education faces hurdles due to complexities (Abbas & Graepel, 2024). Therefore, this research aims to (1) examine the correlation between students' utilization of AI tools and their chosen field of study; (2) explore undergraduate students' perceptions of the application of AI in their academic research; and (3) analyze the perceived significance of AI integration within the context of specific majors.

AI Integration in Higher Education

This evolution of AI has been gradually propagated as having strategic value for education. AI could be a fruitful learning tool for both teachers and students, and it offers effective learning experiences for students (Zhai et al., 2021; Sam et al., 2024; Sam et al., 2012 a; Sam et al., 2012 b; Sam et al., 2013 a; Sam et al., 2013b). There is a need to improve the academic understanding of artificial intelligence in education (AIED) because the field is expanding

and changing quickly. Zawacki-Richter et al. (2019) called attention to the need to deepen our understanding of AIED's potential in educational settings. Crompton & Burke (2023) reported that AI was used as an assistant in high education. According to Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019; Luttrell et al., 2020 (as cited in Zhang & Aslan, 2021), multidisciplinary techniques are necessary for applications in education (AIED) because the majority of AI research is limited to STEM subjects. The fields that had the most uses of AIED research projects were engineering, computer science, information technology (IT), mathematics, foreign languages, science, and business. STEM fields accounted for 25 out of the 40 key research projects that were published in AIED. Six key themes from the main study fields were identified: chatbots; expert systems; intelligent tutors or agents; machine learning; and personalized learning systems and visualizations (Hutson, 2022). According to Chen et al. (2020), two early examples of AI in education were computer-assisted instruction (CAI) and intelligent tutoring systems (ITSs), which provide students with quick feedback and tailored learning experiences. Through the evolution of these systems, increasingly advanced tools that assist teaching and learning have been produced by combining machine learning and natural language processing. Additional empirical research has shown how important learning analytics is for promoting student achievement. To deliver insightful feedback and interventions, learning analytics involves gathering and evaluating data about students and learning environments. Large-scale empirical confirmation of the efficacy of learning analytics is still needed, despite its potential. However, according to recent research, learning analytics can help identify students who are at risk and improve their academic performance (Ifenthaler & Yau, 2020). Furthermore, the importance of employing evidence-based learning activities that enhance academic performance beyond individual student attributes such as enthusiasm and prior knowledge is highlighted by empirical studies (Bosch et al., 2021). All of these results point to how important empirical data are in creating

sensible higher education practices and regulations (Barnes & Hutson, 2024).

AI literacy

The definition of "literacy" has expanded from its original meaning of the ability to read and write to more recent conceptualizations. Literacy now encompasses the ability to identify, understand, interpret, create, communicate, and calculate via printed and written materials across various contexts (Domínguez Figaredo & Stoyanovich, 2023). The term "AI literacy" used by researchers in the current study emphasizes the importance of including AI as a digital literacy skill for everyone in the 21st century (Su et al., 2023). Salhab (2024) defined AI literacy as an essential pillar of higher education that requires proficiencies and knowledge to effectively fulfill practical activities expected of both teachers and students within the educational context of employing AI. During the early 2000s, interest in AI-based educational technologies, particularly those aimed at improving technical literacy, significantly increased. Virtual labs and simulations have emerged as popular methods for teaching technical subjects, enabling students to conduct experiments and understand concepts in a virtual setting. These tools provide interactive learning experiences and allow educators to monitor student performance in real time, facilitating tailored instruction. In more recent years, the incorporation of AI in education has progressed, with a focus on personalized learning and adaptive technologies. AI-driven platforms now deliver customized learning experiences that address the specific needs of individual students, offering targeted instruction and support. Furthermore, AI-based tools such as chatbots and virtual assistants have become more prevalent, providing students with immediate access to information and assistance. In addition, AI literacy can be defined as the capacity to comprehend and critically assess the knowledge, values, and cultures influencing AI systems and the effects of AI-generated content. It entails an understanding of the particular cultural, social, and political contexts within which AI systems function, as well as the potential for biased decisions on the basis of

demographic characteristics such as race and gender (Chu-Ke & Dong, 2024; Chhor et al. 2024; Chin et al., 2024; Keo et al., 2024).

Ethical Considerations of AI in Education

The highest priority is given to ethical issues in accordance with the study topic. To preserve academic integrity and prevent plagiarism, the information gathered from the literature study is correctly credited to its sources. Furthermore, the privacy and data protection of the people referenced in the chosen sources were respected. When implementing AI in education or any other profession, ethical considerations are crucial since employing nontraditional approaches might be viewed as "cheating" by others. The communication of inaccurate assessment findings can occur when attempts are made to cheat and when information collection is poor. Universities that award degrees should be reliable references that companies use to choose the most qualified candidates for their positions. Long-term repercussions will be faced by both graduates and those who do not acquire the abilities they should have during their academic careers (Leta & Vancea, 2023). Artificial intelligence (AI) in education has the ability to completely transform the way students learn by offering them cutting-edge instructional tools, personalized training, and a reduction in administrative responsibilities. The rapid use of AI technology raises a number of ethical challenges that must be addressed to ensure the responsible and ethical deployment of this technology. Data privacy, algorithmic bias, transparency, and the impact on the role of educators are important topics to discuss when discussing AI in education. These ethical concerns must be carefully managed to protect the rights and interests of all parties participating in the educational environment and make appropriate use of the benefits of AI (Remian, 2019).

1. Security of Data and Privacy: Education AI systems sometimes require a great deal of personal data from students, including identities, behavioral patterns, and academic transcripts. Ensuring that information is used responsibly and maintained securely to prevent breaches and

unauthorized access is known as data protection. If not, informed consent should be obtained from the students or their guardians before their data are gathered and used (Reiss, 2021). To date, utilizing AI in education involves gathering and analyzing massive amounts of student data. It is vital to protect this information. Adequate data security protocols are necessary to guard against the loss and improper use of private information. Families and students should also have access to manage student data, including the ability to access, modify, and delete information. An increasing number of recommendations and rules are being made in the area of ethical artificial intelligence. The European Commission recently published guidelines for trustworthy and moral AI. According to these guidelines, situations involving weaker people and power or information disparities should be given more consideration. Fundamental rights, social norms, and the moral precepts of explainability and prevention should serve as the foundation for AI. In addition to being technically sound and adhering to rules and regulations, it should also consider issues of harm, justice, and human autonomy. These guidelines are designed to protect vulnerable patients from social hierarchy and uncertainty. They align with the fundamental medical ethics precepts of beneficence, nonmaleficence, justice, and human autonomy.

2. Privacy and Data Protection: Data protection and privacy are two important areas of ethical concern. AI systems' massive gathering and processing of student data raises concerns about data security, privacy, and possible misuse. To address the issues raised by AI in education (Floridi et al., 2021), a thorough framework of information ethics must be established. To protect students' right to privacy, the author highlights the significance of user control and transparency (Nguyen et al., 2022).

3. Digital Gap and Availability: The current digital divide may worsen as a result of AI integration in education. Not every student has access to the internet and technology needed to use AI-driven teaching resources (Akgun & Greenhow, 2022). Owing to this discrepancy,

pupils from lower socioeconomic backgrounds may not have as many learning opportunities as their peers do. To further exacerbate this disparity, schools in poor districts may find it difficult to maintain and acquire cutting-edge AI equipment. It is imperative to guarantee fair access to AI resources to prevent the exacerbation of educational disparities. AI in education has a significant effect on teachers and students alike, resulting in opportunities and difficulties that need to be carefully considered (Klimova et al., 2023).

4. Instructor role transformation: AI frees up teachers to focus more on the creative and engaging aspects of teaching by automating administrative tasks such as grading and attendance. However, because of this shift, educators may need to adapt to new technology and reevaluate their conventional duties. First, professional development for teachers is needed for training to successfully integrate AI tools into their lesson plans. This involves being able to use AI to suit the different needs of students and customize training while maintaining human touch (Slade & Prinsloo, 2013). Second, ethical responsibilities are also important. Teachers must be aware of the moral implications of AI, including privacy concerns and algorithmic bias. They play a crucial role in monitoring AI decisions and ensuring that they are implemented in a fair and open manner (Cerratto Pargman & McGrath, 2021). Job security concern is one of the things to consider, as some tasks are automated. Teachers may start to worry about their job security. A balance needs to be struck between using AI to increase productivity and preserving the essential human element in education (Corrin et al., 2019; Lan et al., 2024a; Lan et al., 2024b).

5. Students' Personalized Learning: AI is able to provide learning experiences that are uniquely customized for every student, taking into consideration both their strengths and shortcomings. As a result, both learning outcomes and engagement could increase. It also raises concerns over data privacy and possible overreliance on technology (Tzimas & Demetriadis, 2021). AI in education enhances skill development by preparing pupils for a

technologically driven environment by promoting the development of technical and digital literacy. Ensuring that students develop their critical thinking with creativity and problem-solving skills at the same time is crucial. Equity and Access: The fact that some students do not have equal access to AI technologies may lead to disparities in educational opportunities. Ensuring that AI benefits all students, irrespective of their financial situation, is a significant ethical challenge.

Challenges of AI Integration in Education

According to previous researchers, AI tools have provided many opportunities for learners. In contrast, all around the world are concerned with AI applications in universities. Researchers and international organizations and governments in every country stated the risk of using AI, such as Pedro et al. (2019), who highlighted six key challenges in the application of AI in education. These include the need for a comprehensive public policy on AI for sustainable development, ensuring that AI in education promotes inclusion and equity, preparing teachers for AI-enhanced education while also equipping AI systems to understand educational contexts, and developing quality and inclusive data systems. Additionally, they emphasized the importance of conducting meaningful research on AI in education and maintaining ethics and transparency in the collection, use, and dissemination of data. The potential for job displacement, the need to ensure data privacy and security, and the risk that AI-driven transformations may exacerbate existing inequalities in higher education. Students may become overly reliant on AI tools, which could hinder the development of critical cognitive skills such as critical thinking and problem solving. Additionally, if not carefully designed, AI algorithms may introduce biases that affect cognitive assessments. Shabir & Arsalan (2024) stated that AI applications in education challenges include technical infrastructure and support, ethical consideration, personalization and customization, teacher training and professional development, access and equity, interdisciplinary collaboration, continuous evaluation and improvement,

cultural and societal acceptance, and legal and regulatory frameworks. AI application in graduate schools is key for making future decisions for every institute in Cambodia because of its complexity of opportunities and risks of insecurity in the modern era. The results AI application has not yet been declared by any organizations or encouraged to apply it individually by students in Battambang, Cambodia. However, the students themselves have decisions connected informally to AI in their academic work. Better than do nothing, we are going through their opinions on applying AI in their academic work.

Benefits of AI Integration in Education

Industry 4.0, also referred to as the Fourth Industrial Revolution or 4IR, characterizes the present phase of advanced manufacturing technology. It encompasses elements such as connectivity, analytics, and automation and disruptive trends such as data-driven processes, human-machine interactions, and robotics. Essentially, Industry 4.0 aims to integrate smart technologies to revolutionize production systems, increase productivity, and improve energy efficiency (McKinsey & Company, 2022). In addition, Yang & Wang (2023) described AI students with the greatest ability in depth as intelligent students: “advantages given by AI tools truly enjoyable in the ChatGPT can pass the national teacher certificate examination. This reflects that AI can attract academic work in universities. In addition, Debo (2024) described the advantages of AI: personalizing learning, providing experiences for students, assisting students with helping with AI, analyzing students’ performance, identifying knowledge gaps, providing suitable materials and exercises to improve students’ learning outcomes, increasing engagement, and reducing the dropout rate of students. Similarly, Suleman & Abbas (2024) reported that AI has emerged to revolutionize traditional teaching and learning practices:

Chatbots support virtual assistants, answer students' questions, provide resources, and facilitate communication between learners and educators. It is useful for finding an appropriate

solution of complexity in academic works. It helps learners achieve higher academic performance in their school. In contrast, the researcher often addressed the suffering of AI applications that threaten the modern world with out-of-control processes.

Materials and Methods

The research approach that the authors use is the quantitative research approach. The process focuses on collecting data from 370 students at 3 different universities in Battambang Province. The questionnaire was used by our group, and closed-ended questions were available for the research questions. The data will be collected from the students in NUBB, UME and SUBB by selecting from years 1 to 4 in 5 faculties. Three universities in Battambang are involved: the National University of Battambang (NUBB), the University of Management and Economics (UME) and Preah Sihanouk raja Buddhist University (SUBB). There are 370 respondents from the three universities. They are from years 1--4 of a bachelor's degree. Five faculties are selected for collecting data: Language Education, Agriculture Science, Engineering, BBA, and Social Science. Tools involve collecting data such as questionnaire papers, cameras for taking photos, notebooks and pens for taking notes, planning papers for checking the process of collecting data, motorbikes for traveling in the process of collecting data, registration forms for registering at the three universities, computers for saving the data for analysis, and SPSS for analyzing the data collected from the respondents.

Results

Table 1. Questionnaire Reliability

Categories	Number of items	Alpha
Utilize of AI	10	.750
Students' Perception On AI	10	.817
Significance of AI Integration	10	.829

The reliability of the questionnaires used in the study is demonstrated by satisfactory Cronbach's alpha values, indicating good internal consistency across the three main categories assessed. The utilization of the AI category, which includes 10 items, has an alpha value of .750, suggesting a reliable measurement of AI usage. The Students' Perception of AI category, which also comprises 10 items, has a higher alpha value of .817, indicating strong consistency in capturing students' attitudes toward AI. The highest reliability is found in the significance of AI integration category, with an alpha value of .829 for its 10 items, reflecting a robust measure of the perceived importance of AI integration in students' academic and future professional lives.

Table 2. Demographic Profile

Items		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	100	27.0
	Female	271	73.0
Participants' age	17	5	1.3
	18	22	5.9
	19	50	13.5
	20	84	22.6
	21	86	23.2
	22	65	17.5
	23	28	7.5
	24	13	3.5
	25	7	1.9
	26	6	1.6
	27	2	.5
	30	1	.3
	31	1	.3
35	1	.3	
Education	Year 1	69	18.6
	Year 2	85	22.9
	Year 3	182	49.1
	Year 4	3	9.4
Major	Language Education	75	20.2
	Agriculture Science	24	6.5
	BBA	104	28.0
	Engineering	24	6.5
	Social Science	45	12.1
	Other	99	26.7

The gender distribution among the participants shows a significant disparity, with females

making up 73.0% of the sample, compared to 27.0% males. This suggests that the study predominantly represents female perspectives. Regarding age, the majority of participants fall within the 18 to 22 age range, with the highest representation being 21-year-olds at 23.2%. The smallest age groups are those above 30, indicating that the sample primarily consists of younger individuals. In terms of education, a substantial proportion of participants are in their

third year (49.1%), followed by second-year students (22.9%). First-year students account for 18.6%, and fourth-year students are the least represented at 9.4%. The participants' majors are diverse, with the largest group studying BBA (28.0%), followed by those in unspecified "Other" majors (26.7%) and Language Education (20.2%). Smaller numbers are found in Social Science (12.1%), Agriculture Science (6.5%), and Engineering (6.5%).

Table 3. Utilization of AI

Items	Statements	Level of Frequency %				M	SD
		N	R	S	O		
UA1	I use Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools or applications for my academic work.	10.2	11.3	45.0	33.4	3.02	.927
UA2	I use Google Translate to support my understanding for English lessons.	1.1	2.7	30.2	66.0	3.61	.598
UA3	I use Grammarly tools to Improve my writing in English.	19.7	24.0	37.5	18.9	2.56	1.010
UA4	I use ChatGPT to generate ideas to support my assignments and homework.	27.8	23.5	33.4	15.4	2.36	1.047
UA5	I use Bing or Copilot to support my assignments and homework.	47.2	22.4	21.3	9.2	1.92	1.024
UA6	I use QuillBot to support my assignments and homework.	53.6	19.7	18.9	7.8	1.81	1.002
UA7	I am interested in using other AI tools for doing assignments and homework.	5.7	17.3	49.1	28.0	2.99	.825
UA8	I use AI applications for research on my computer.	10.0	22.1	40.2	27.8	2.86	.938
UA9	I use AI tools for research on my smartphone.	7.0	9.2	36.4	47.4	3.24	.889
UA10	I spend time using AI at my school's computer lab for research.	27.2	30.2	29.9	12.7	2.28	1.001

*Level of Frequency: 1= Never, 2= Rarely, 3= Sometimes, 4= Often

Participants display varied patterns in their utilization of AI tools for academic purposes, with most engaging with these technologies to some extent. Google Translate is particularly popular, with 66.0% of participants using it often, resulting in a high mean score of 3.61. Grammarly is used sometimes by 37.5% of participants, indicating its moderate integration into writing activities. ChatGPT is utilized to generate ideas, with 33.4% using it sometimes,

though 27.8% have never used it. Tools like Bing/Copilot and QuillBot have lower usage rates, with the majority rarely or never using them. There is a notable interest in exploring other AI tools, as 49.1% sometimes express interest, and 28.0% often do. AI applications for research are commonly used on smartphones, with 47.4% using them often, highlighting the mobile accessibility of AI tools in academic research.

Table 4. Students' Perception

Items	Statements	Level of Agreement %				M	SD
		SD	D	A	SA		
SP1	I feel comfortable using AI for my research.	.5	4.9	60.6	34.0	3.28	.576
SP2	AI gives me a lot of benefits in my major.	1.1	3.8	56.6	38.5	3.33	.601
SP3	Using AI can help me to save my time in the study process.	.5	4.0	60.4	35.0	3.30	.569
SP4	AI helps enhance the level of my study to be better.	1.1	11.1	59.8	28.0	3.15	.643
SP5	I use AI to gain the main idea to support assigned tasks.	1.1	7.5	65.8	25.6	3.16	.592
SP6	AI makes my traditional learning more effective.	1.6	18.6	64.7	15.1	2.93	.631
SP7	I think AI is a reliable tool for my research.	1.1	21.8	61.5	15.6	2.92	.642
SP8	AI can help me to release stress in my field of study.	1.9	12.9	65.5	19.7	3.03	.634
SP9	AI tools help accelerate my research to be more effective.	.8	5.4	63.9	29.9	3.23	.578
SP10	I mainly use AI tools to check my writing, grammar, spelling and others.	3.2	20.2	60.6	15.9	2.89	.693

*Level of Agreement: 1= Strongly Disagree, 2= Disagree, 3= Agree, 4= Strongly Agree

Students generally perceive AI positively, recognizing its various benefits in their academic pursuits. A high comfort level with using AI for research is evident, with 60.6% agreeing and 34.0% strongly agreeing. Participants also acknowledge the substantial benefits AI provides in their major fields, with 56.6% agreeing and 38.5% strongly agreeing. The time-

saving aspect of AI is widely appreciated, as indicated by 60.4% agreeing and 35.0% strongly agreeing. Furthermore, many students believe that AI helps alleviate stress related to their studies, with 65.5% agreeing and 19.7% strongly agreeing, showcasing the supportive role of AI in managing academic pressures.

Table 5. Significance of AI Integration

Items	Statements	Level of Importance %				M	SD
		VU	U	I	VI		
SA1	I experienced that AI has contributed a great help in my study field.	.5	4.9	60.6	34.0	3.19	.537
SA2	AI helps me to develop my knowledge better in my major.	1.1	3.8	56.6	38.5	3.20	.566
SA3	AI tools establish some clue information for my work.	.5	4.0	60.4	35.0	3.16	.624
SA4	AI can help me to support my career performance in the workplace.	1.1	11.1	59.8	28.0	2.86	.662
SA5	AI is a special tool for me to develop my flexibility in my major.	1.1	7.5	65.8	25.6	3.10	.609
SA6	expect that carefully choosing appropriate AI tools for my research is useful.	1.6	18.6	64.7	15.1	3.23	.577
SA7	AI can give me clues and solutions when I face difficulty in my work research.	1.1	21.8	61.5	15.6	3.27	.579
SA8	I expect that my university will have licensed AI tools for college students for research and studying.	1.9	12.9	65.5	19.7	3.30	.624
SA9	I think AI is necessary for my case studies.	.8	5.4	63.9	29.9	3.19	.612

SA10	AI can help me to develop my knowledge better and reasonably in 21st century education.	3.2	20.2	60.6	15.9	3.37	.585
*Level of Importance: 1= Very Unimportant, 2= Unimportant, 3=Important, 4= Very Important							

The integration of AI in academic and professional contexts is regarded as highly significant by the participants. A majority (60.6% important, 34.0% very important) believe that AI has greatly contributed to their study fields. AI is also seen as a valuable tool for knowledge development in their majors, with 56.6% finding it important and 38.5% very important. In regard to career performance, views are mixed but generally positive, with 59.8% considering it important and 28.0% very important. The necessity of AI for case studies is emphasized by 63.9% of participants who find it important and 29.9% who view it as very important. Participants also express a strong expectation for universities to provide licensed AI tools to support research and studying, reflecting the growing reliance on AI in academic environments.

Conclusion

The study reveals a predominantly positive reception and significant utilization of AI tools among students, particularly those in the younger age brackets and third year of study. The gender distribution shows greater female representation, whereas the diversity in majors highlights a broad perspective on AI's role in education. The high reliability of the questionnaires confirms the credibility of these findings. Students widely use AI tools such as Google Translate and show substantial interest in exploring new AI technologies. They perceive AI as beneficial for saving time, enhancing academic work, and reducing stress. However, the varying usage levels of different AI tools indicate potential areas for increased awareness and integration. The strong demand for institutional support in providing licensed AI tools underscores the critical role that universities can play in facilitating AI adoption. By addressing barriers to AI utilization and

promoting effective integration strategies, educational institutions can further enhance the academic experiences and future career prospects of their students. Overall, the integration of AI in undergraduate studies at Battambang universities has significant potential to enhance educational outcomes through personalized learning and improved student engagement. However, this study highlights several critical challenges, including the lack of formal training for students, concerns about data privacy, and ethical implications. To fully realize the benefits of AI in education, it is essential for educators, policymakers, and technology developers to collaborate in creating robust frameworks that address these challenges. This includes ensuring equitable access to AI tools, maintaining transparency in data usage, and prioritizing ethical considerations. By doing so, AI can be effectively integrated into higher education, providing students with the necessary skills and knowledge to thrive in a technologically advanced world.

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Conflict of Interest

There are no conflicts of interest.

References

Abbas, B. & Graepel, T. (2024). *Adapting to AI Education: Overcoming Challenges in Generative AI Integration*. Department of Computer Science, University of Cambridge. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16857.53605>

- Akgun, S., & Greenhow, C. (2022). Artificial intelligence in education: Addressing ethical challenges in K-12 settings. *AI and Ethics*, 2(3), 431-440. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43681-021-00096-7>
- Barnes, E., & Hutson, J. (2024). Strategic Integration of AI in Higher Education and Industry: The AI8-Point Model. *Advances in Social Sciences and Management*, 2(6). <https://doi.org/10.63002/assm.26.520>
- Bosch, E., Seifried, E., & Spinath, B. (2021). What successful students do: Evidence-based learning activities matter for students' performance in higher education beyond prior knowledge, motivation, and prior achievement. *Learning and Individual Differences*, 91, 102056. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lindif.2021.102056>
- Chhor, C., Sek, V., Norng, R., and Sam, R. (2024). Relationship of Intrinsic and Extrinsic Factors Motivating EFL Students toward Learning English: A Case Study of the National University of Battambang. *Research Square* <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-4892574/v1>
- Chin, P., Sam, R., Serey, M., & Em, S. (2024). Exploring the Benefits and Drawbacks of Directing Undergraduates' Self-Study Pursuits: An In-depth Analysis through Literature Review. *Journal of General Education and Humanities*, 3(2), 117-132. <https://doi.org/10.58421/gehu.v3i2.210>
- Chen, L., Chen, P., & Lin, Z. (2020). Artificial intelligence in education: A review. *Ieee Access*, 8, 75264-75278. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2988510>
- Chu-Ke, C., & Dong, Y. (2024). Misinformation and literacies in the era of generative artificial intelligence: A brief overview and a call for future research. *Emerging Media*, 2(1), 70-85. <https://doi.org/10.1177/27523543241240285>
- Cerratto Pargman, T., & McGrath, C. (2021). Mapping the ethics of learning analytics in higher education: A systematic literature review of empirical research. *Journal of Learning Analytics*, 8(2), 123-139. <https://doi.org/10.18608/jla.2021.1>
- Crompton, H., & Burke, D. (2023). Artificial intelligence in higher education: The state of the field. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 20, Article 8. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-023-00392-8>
- Domínguez Figaredo, D., & Stoyanovich, J. (2023). Responsible AI literacy: A stakeholder-first approach. *Big Data & Society*, 10(2), 20539517231219958. <https://doi.org/10.1177/20539517231219958>
- Floridi, L., Cowls, J., King, T. C., & Taddeo, M. (2021). How to design AI for social good: Seven essential factors. *Ethics, Governance, and Policies in Artificial Intelligence*, 125-151. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11948-020-00213-5>
- George, B. & Wooden, O. (2023). *Managing the Strategic Transformation of Higher Education through Artificial Intelligence*. Administrative Sciences,1. <https://doi.org/10.3390/admsci13090196>
- Hutson, J. (2022). Artificial Intelligence and the Disruption of Higher Education: Strategies for Integrations across Disciplines. *Scientific Research Publishing*, 3959. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ce.2022.1312253>
- Ifenthaler, D., & Yau, J. Y. K. (2020). Utilizing learning analytics to support study success in higher education: a systematic review. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 68(4), 1961-1990. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11423-020-09788-z>
- Jameel, T., & Arsalan, H. (2024). Adapting Education for the AI Era: Strategies for Generative AI Integration. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.10251.50723>
- Klimova, B., Pikhart, M., & Kacetl, J. (2023). Ethical issues of the use of AI-driven mobile apps for education. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 10, 1118116. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2022.1118116>
- Keo, Vireak., Sam, R., Lan, B., & Wen, R. (2024). Challenges And Opportunities Of Educational Technology Integration In Cambodian Higher Education Institutions: A Literature Review. *International Journal of Education, Psychology and Counseling*, 9(54), 157-176.

- Lan, B., Sam, R., Keo, V., & Roet, W. (2024a). Academic Adjustment of Freshmen in Cambodian Higher Education Institutions: A Systematic Literature Review. *Journal of General Education and Humanities*, 3(2), 169–196. <https://doi.org/10.58421/gehu.v3i2.203>
- Lan, B., Sam, R., Keo, V., & Rouet, W. (2024b). Factors Influencing Academic Adjustment and Learning Outcomes in Higher Education Institutions in Battambang: A Conceptual Framework. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(5), 9-30. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(5\).02](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(5).02)
- Nguyen, A., Järvelä, S., Wang, Y., & Rosé, C. P. (2022). Exploring socially shared regulation with an AI deep learning approach using multimodal data. In *Proceedings of the 16th International Conference of the Learning Sciences-ICLS 2022*, pp. 527-534. International Society of the Learning Sciences. <https://dx.doi.org/10.22318/icls2022.527>
- Reiss, M. J. (2021). The use of AI in education: Practicalities and ethical considerations. *London Review of Education*, 19(1). <https://doi.org/10.14324/lre.19.1.05>
- Slade, S., & Prinsloo, P. (2013). Learning analytics: Ethical issues and dilemmas. *American Behavioral Scientist*, 57(10), 1510-1529. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0002764213479366>
- Sol, K., Heng, K., & Sok, S. (2024). Using AI in English language education: An exploration of Cambodian EFL university students' experiences, perceptions, and attitudes. *Perceptions, and Attitudes*. <https://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4687461>
- Su, J., Ng, D. T. K., & Chu, S. K. W. (2023). Artificial intelligence (AI) literacy in early childhood education: The challenges and opportunities. *Computers and Education: Artificial Intelligence*, 4, 100124. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.caeai.2023.100124>
- Salhab, R. (2024). AI Literacy across Curriculum Design: Investigating College Instructors' Perspectives. *Online Learning*, 28(2), n2. <https://doi:10.24059/olj.v28i2.4426>
- Suleman, M., & Abbas, A. (2024) Navigating the Integration of AI in Education: Challenges and Opportunities for Learning and Teaching. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.11326.29769>
- Shabir, W., & Arsalan, H. (2024). Generative AI in Education: Strategies for Addressing Implementation Challenges. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.24721.85601>
- Tieng, M., Yoeng, H., Sam, R., Nhean, V., Hour, R., and Doern, E. (2023). Institutional Integration Factors That Impact Students' Academic and Intellectual Developments: A Case Study of Three Cambodian Rural Universities. *International Journal of Learning and Development*, 13(3), 39-64, <https://doi.org/10.5296/ijld.v13i3.21106>
- Yang, X., Wang, Q., & Lyu, J. (2023). Assessing ChatGPT's educational capabilities and application potential. *ECNU Review of Education*, 20965311231210006. <https://doi.org/10.1177/20965311231210006>
- Zhai, X., Chu, X., Chai, C. S., Jong, M. S. Y., Istenic, A., Spector, M., Liu, J.-B., Yuan, J., & Li, Y. (2021). *A review of artificial intelligence (AI) in education from 2010 to 2020*. Wiley Online Library. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/8812542>
- Zawacki-Richter, O., Marín, V. I., Bond, M., & Gouverneur, F. (2019). Systematic review of research on artificial intelligence applications in higher education: Where are the educators? *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 16, 1-27. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-019-0171-0>
- Zhang, K., & Aslan, A. B. (2021). AI technologies for education: Recent research & future directions. *Computers and Education: Artificial Intelligence*, 2, 100025. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.caeai.2021.100025>
- Debo, D. (2024). AI in Higher Education: Opportunities and Challenges. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/380668892_AI_in_Higher_Education_Opportunities_and_Challenges

- Corrin, L., Kennedy, G., French, S., Buckingham Shum S., Kitto, K., Pardo, A., West, D., Mirriahi, N., & Colvin, C. (2019). The Ethics of Learning Analytics in Australian Higher Education. A Discussion Paper. melbourne-cshe.unimelb.edu.au/research/research-projects/edutech/the-ethical-use-of-learning-analytics
- Leta, F. M., & Vancea, D. P. C. (2023). Ethics in Education: Exploring the Ethical Implications of Artificial Intelligence Implementation. *Ovidius University Annals, Economic Sciences Series*, 23(1), 413-421.
- McKinsey & Company. (2022, August 17). What is Industry 4.0 and Fourth Industrial Revolution. <https://www.mckinsey.com/feature-d-insights/mckinsey-explainers/what-are-industry-4-0-the-fourth-industrial-revolution-and-4ir>
- Pedro, F., Subosa, M., Rivas, A., & Valverde, P. (2019). Artificial intelligence in education: Challenges and opportunities for sustainable development. <https://hdl.handle.net/20.500.12799/6533>
- Remian, D. (2019). Augmenting education: ethical considerations for incorporating artificial intelligence in education. https://scholarworks.umb.edu/instruction_capstone/52
- Sam, R., Yoeng, H., Tieng, M., and Chiv, S. (2024). Factors Influencing English-Speaking Anxiety Among EFL Learners: A Case Study in Cambodian Higher Education, *Research Square*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-4497347/v1>
- Sam, R., Ahmad, N., & Hazril, J. (2012a). Cambodia's Higher Education Development in Historical Perspectives (1863-2012). *International Journal of Learning and Development*, 2(2), 224-241. <https://doi.org/10.5296/ijld.v2i2.1670>
- Sam, R., Ahmad, N., & Hazril, J. (2012b). Establishment of Institutional Policies for Enhancing Education Quality in Cambodian Universities. *International Journal of Higher Education*, 1(1), 112-127. <https://doi.org/10.5430/ijhe.v1n1p112>
- Sam, R., Souriyawongsa T., Ahmad, N., & Hazril, J. (2013 a). Investigating the Institutional Policies that contribute toward the Students' Academic Success in a Cambodian University. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 3(1), 113-124.
- Sam, R., Ahmad, N., & Hazril, J. (2013 b). "Conceptualizing Institutional Policies for Students' Academic Success in Cambodian Universities: What matters for policy?". *Asian Social Science*, 9(10), 283-294. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ass.v9n10p283>
- Sarin, S., & Kimkong, H. Generative AI in higher education: The need to develop or revise academic integrity policies to ensure the ethical use of AI in Cambodia. <https://www.cd-center.org/category/publication/education/>
- Tzimas, D., & Demetriadis, S. N. (2021, June). The Impact of Learning Analytics on Student Performance and Satisfaction in a Higher Education Course. In *EDM*. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/353803495_The_Impact_of_Learning_Analytics_on_Student_Performance_and_Satisfaction_in_a_Higher_Education_Course